

MODY mutations in transcription factors HNF1A and HNF1B affect the production of interferon signaling proteins: evidence at the proteome level

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Supplementary figures

A. Stage4

All identified proteins

B. Stage4

Differentially abundant proteins

C. Stage0

All identified proteins

D. Stage0

Differentially abundant proteins

Figure S.1: Venn diagram of identified and differentially abundant proteins in hiPSC datasets

A. Comparison of all identified proteins in stage 4 pancreatic progenitor cells using DDA and DIA mass spectrometry methods. B. Differentially abundant proteins in stage 4 cells identified by DDA and DIA. C. Comparison of all identified proteins in stage 0 stem cells using DDA and DIA. D. Differentially abundant proteins in stage 0 cells identified by DDA and DIA.

A. Stage 4 DDA

B. Stage 4 DIA

Figure S.2: Volcano plots of differentially abundant proteins in stage 4 pancreatic progenitor cells Comparison of cells with the HNF1A frameshift mutation to control cells. Colors highlight proteins related to interferon signaling and energy exchange pathways identified by Qiagen IPA.

A. DDA mass spectrometry dataset. B. DIA mass spectrometry dataset.

A. Stage 0 DDA

B. Stage 0 DIA

Figure S.3: Volcano plots of differentially abundant proteins in stage 0 stem cells Comparison of cells with the HNF1A frameshift mutation to control cells. Colors highlight proteins related to interferon signaling and energy exchange pathways identified by Qiagen IPA.

A. DDA mass spectrometry dataset. B. DIA mass spectrometry dataset.

A. Stage 4 DDA

B. Stage 4 DIA

C. Stage 0 DDA

D. Stage 0 DIA

Figure S.4: Most significantly enriched pathways predicted by Qiagen IPA Based on differentially abundant proteins with at least 2-fold change and BH-adjusted p-values < 0.05. Z-scores indicate the direction of regulation (≥ 2). Plots show the top 12 pathways selected by z-scores.

Figure S.5: Heat map of the most regulated pathways predicted by Qiagen IPA. This heat map illustrates the most regulated pathways predicted by Qiagen IPA software, comparing pathways enriched across all datasets. The color indicates z-scores, showing the direction and magnitude of regulation. The figure demonstrates the reproducibility of the most regulated pathways among the datasets. **Mtx** Energy exchange-related pathways show consistent regulation in both stage 0 and stage 4, while **IS** interferon signaling-related pathways are only downregulated in samples at stage 4.

A. Stage 4 DDA

B. Stage 4 DIA

C. Stage 0 DDA

D. Stage 0 DIA

Figure S.6: Hallmark gene set enrichment of downregulated proteins Analysis performed by FragPipe-Analyst tool across all hiPSC datasets.

A. Stage 0 STRING clustering

Figure S.8: Protein interaction analysis in stage 0 stem cells Performed by STRING on differentially abundant proteins. MCL clustering with inflation parameter 3.

A. Network of all proteins with highlighted clusters. B. Oxidative Phosphorylation/Mitochondrial ATP Synthesis Coupled Electron Transport cluster.

Figure S.9: Differentially abundant proteins in RPTEC cells with S148L substitution in HNF1B compared to the wild type (A). IPA pathway enrichment analysis (B.), Hallmark gene sets enrichment (C.)

Interferon alpha/beta signaling,
Guanylate-binding protein, C-
terminal

Figure S.10: Protein interaction analysis in RPTEC cells Performed by STRING on differentially abundant proteins. MCL clustering with inflation parameter 3.